

The coherent magnetic field of the Milky Way halo, the Local Bubble, and the Fan region

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ABSTRACT

Context. A recent catalogue of the Faraday rotation measures (RMs) of extragalactic sources, together with the synchrotron polarisation data from WMAP and *Planck*, provide us with a wealth of information on the magnetic fields of the Galaxy. However, the integral character of these observables, together with our position inside the Galaxy, make the inference of the coherent Galactic magnetic field (GMF) complicated and ambiguous.

Aims. We combine several phenomenological components of the GMF — the spiral arms, the toroidal halo, the X-shaped field, and the field of the Local Bubble — to construct a new model of the regular GMF outside the thin disc.

Methods. We use the binned χ^2 approach to fit the parameters of the model to the data. To have control over the relative contributions of the RM and polarisation data to the fit, we pay special attention to the estimation of errors in data bins. To this end, we developed a systematic method that is uniformly applicable to different data sets. This method takes into account individual measurement errors, the variance in the bin, and fluctuations in the data at angular scales that are larger than the bin size. This leads to a decrease in the errors and, as a result, to better sensitivity of the data to the model content. We cross checked the stability of our method with the new LOFAR data, which have very small errors on the measurements of individual sources.

Results. We find that the four components listed above are sufficient to fit both the RM and polarisation data over the whole sky with only a small fraction masked out. Moreover, we have achieved several important improvements compared to previous approaches. Due to our location inside of the Local Bubble, our model does not require the introduction of striated fields. For the first time, we show that the Fan region can be modelled as a Galactic-scale feature. The pitch angle of the magnetic field in our fit converges to a value of around 20 degrees. Interestingly, this value is very close to the direction of the spiral arms inferred recently from *Gaia* data on upper-main sequence stars.

Key words. Galaxies: magnetic fields, ISM: magnetic fields, cosmic rays

Appendix C: Details of the final fit and comparison with existing models

In this section we present a comparison of our model with the base model of Unger & Farrar (2024). In order to reproduce the results of Unger & Farrar (2024) we switched to the thermal electron model of Yao et al. (2017), recomputed cosmic ray electron distribution following the prescriptions given in Unger & Farrar (2024) and included the effect of the striated field.

The bin by bin performances of the models are shown in Figs. C.2 C.3 C.4. Our model and the model of Unger & Farrar (2024) were fitted assuming different masks on the data. Apart from small-scale features, the main difference between the masks comes from the Galactic plane and the Fan region. The Galactic plane in the RM data is excluded in our analysis, while present in the analysis of Unger & Farrar (2024). To the contrary, in the polarisation data the Galactic plane is masked by Unger & Farrar (2024) while included in our fits. Additionally, Unger & Farrar (2024) masked the Fan region on the Stokes Q and U maps. Another two bright radio features Loop I and Loop II were excluded in both analysis in Stokes Q and U .

In summary, our mask is larger for the RM dataset, which can be seen by the absence of data points in the lower panel of Fig. C.2. On the other hand, the mask on the polarisation data is larger in Unger & Farrar (2024). The additional regions masked out by Unger & Farrar (2024) are roughly shown with grey shading in the Figs. C.3 and C.4. We note that the model by Unger & Farrar (2024) does not fit the data in these regions.

As one can see from Figs. C.2 C.3 C.4, in general the predictions of the models are quite similar. However, the direct comparison of the models in terms of χ^2 is not straightforward since they were fitted assuming different masks on the data. For cross-check purposes, the conservative approach would be to compare the models only in those regions where both were fitted. Reproducing roughly the mask of Unger & Farrar (2024) and taking into account only those bins which were included in both analyses we find that the total chi-squared/ndf for our model is $\chi^2 = 1070/717$, while for the base model of Unger & Farrar (2024) one finds $\chi^2 = 1436/717$. Most of the difference comes from the RM data.

Fig. C.1. Spectrum of relativistic leptons. Black dots show the measurements by the AMS-02 experiment. The black curve corresponds to the CRE spectrum calculated with the DRAGON code as described in Sec. 3.3 and used in the analysis. The CRE within the energies indicated with the yellow band produce more than 95% of the synchrotron emission at 23 GHz. The deviation of the AMS-02 measurements below 10 GeV is due to the Solar modulation which we do not take into account.

Fig. C.2. Our best fit model (black line) and UF23 base model (red line) in comparison with the binned RM data (black points with errorbars).
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Fig. C.3. Same as Fig. C.2 but for the Stokes Q parameter. The grey shading roughly indicates the regions which were excluded in the analysis of Unger & Farrar (2024).

Fig. C.4. Same as Fig. C.2 but for the Stokes U parameter.

Fig. C.5. Difference between the data and the model in the units of bins errorbars. The colormap saturates when the difference reaches 3σ level. Left column corresponds to the full model, while the right column shows the residuals for the model with the signal from the Local Bubble removed. The improvements due to the contribution of the Local Bubble are clearly visible in all observables, especially at high Galactic latitudes $|b| > 60^\circ$.

Fig. C.6. Polarised synchrotron intensity of the model in comparison with the WMAP 23 GHz data. The colomap is in the logarithmic scale.